

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D8.2

CINECA Risk Management Registry

WP8: Project Management and coordination

Lead Beneficiary: European Molecular Biology Laboratory

WP leader: Thomas Keane (EMBL-EBI)

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Author of this deliverable: Thomas Keane

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1. Executive Summary

The Purpose of the CINECA Risk Register is to provide the Project Management Team with a list of risks identified, stated clearly and assessed as to their importance to meeting project **objectives**. The identification of mitigations for identified risks in the risk register will facilitate risk handling, should a risk be triggered. The Coordinator and Work Package Leaders, as well as the project manager, will regularly review the Risk Register and update it when necessary.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to enabling clear tracking of project risks. This should enhance the probability of the project achieving all of our objectives in a timely fashion.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

All Work Package Leaders contributed to drafting the document. It has been reviewed by the Project Management Team and approved for submission.

The Risk Register will be utilised for regular monitoring of project progress.

4. Abbreviations

AAI - Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

API - Application Programming Interface

EGA - European Genome-phenome Archive

ELSI - Ethical, Legal and Social Issues

GA4GH - Global Alliance for Genomics and Health

GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation

SME - Small or Medium-sized Enterprise

5. Delivery and schedule

The initial delivery was achieved on time, however this cover page was omitted.

6. Adjustments made

Addition of this cover page for the deliverable, 2nd April, 2019.

Risk register											
Phase select	Risk	Area of project	Risk category	Probability	Impact	Risk score	Risk response	Trigger	Risk owner	Additional Risk owner	Comments
WP5	Lack of services delivered by WP1-4 causes delay in WP5 deliverables	Technical: WP5	deliverable delayed	2	3	6	WP5 will develop applications (DS, 1, DS-3) with the options to replace or switch-out services that are not available or not used in the target countries. Engage clinical scientists early in the process to deliver user defined analysis methodologies and GUIs but also using existing analysis methodologies and GUIs. Provide a framework to simply incorporate new methodologies and standardised analysis.	key technology not available	WP5	WP1	
WP5	Clinical Research and Diagnostic have medical views on how to analyse and report results	Technical: WP5	deliverable does not fulfil scope	2	3	6	Engage clinical scientists early in the process to deliver user defined analysis methodologies and GUIs but also using existing analysis methodologies and GUIs. Provide a framework to simply incorporate new methodologies and standardised analysis.	Issue flagged by WP leader	WP5	WP lead	
WP5	Failure to meet any mandatory national data protection and medical device requirements	Technical: WP5	deliverable does not fulfil scope	1	4	4	Early identification of regulatory data protection or medical device requirements for the project which are subject to device registration that can be met. Timely identification of regulatory data protection or medical device requirements from other key project/infrastructure. Timely circulation of programme	Issue flagged by WP leader	WP5	WP lead	
WP6	Initial stakeholder meeting poorly attended and not representative of CINECA's stakeholders	Technical: WP6	deliverable delayed/does not fulfil scope	4	3	12	Make full use of G4GH, H3AB2BioMed, CANDIG, ELMR, BBMRI to circulate survey	Issue flagged by WP leader	WP6	Coordinator	
WP6	Spreadsheets survey doesn't record appropriate information on the type of objectives	Technical: WP6	deliverable does not fulfil scope	3	3	9	Promote staff visits extensively at the beginning of the project. Promote short courses etc. via existing networks	Issue flagged by WP leader	WP6	Coordinator	
WP6	Poor uptake of non-learning interventions	Technical: WP6	deliverable does not fulfil scope	4	5	20	Promote staff visits extensively at the beginning of the project. Promote short courses etc. via existing networks	other (please specify in comments)	WP6	PMT	Will only be clear in legacy phase of project
WP6	Technical WP6 don't learn outreach, dissemination and Training milestones	project-wide	deliverable delayed	3	3	9	Early engagement with technical WP representatives	deliverable or report due within three months	WP lead	Coordinator	
WP6	Delays to technical deliverables delay final training	project-wide	deliverable delayed	4	3	12	Set dates for final course early and in collaboration with representatives	deliverable or report due within three months	WP lead	Coordinator	
WP7	GDPR and Canadian equivalent laws impeded goals of the project	project-wide	deliverable does not fulfil scope	2	2	4	A key early aim of WP7 is to map the soft and hard law instruments, and international policies across Europe and Canada to inform the project about potential barriers or impediments to personal data sharing	deliverable or report due within three months	WP7	PMT	
WP7	GDPR and Asian equivalent laws impeded goals of the project	project-wide	deliverable does not fulfil scope	4	2	8	Map the soft and hard law instruments, and international policies across Europe and Africa to inform the project about potential barriers or impediments to personal data sharing	deliverable or report due within three months	WP7	PMT	
WP7	Digital market impacts are dependent on our wider engagement with SMEs and the SMEs in the project.	efficacy: WP7	deliverable does not fulfil scope	2	3	6	Engage SMEs early in the project. For example, these may engage EU, changes to the project. For example, these may engage EU, changes to the project. For example, these may engage EU, changes to the project.	deliverable or report due within three months	WP7	PMT	
WP8	Failure in keeping the deliverable and missions timeline	Project management	deliverable delayed/does not fulfil scope	2	3	6	WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board.	deliverable or report due within three months	WP8	Coordinator	
WP8	Break: Effect on UK partners and travel arrangements taken from UK	project-wide	deliverable delayed	3	2	6	WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP8 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board.	other (please specify in comments)	WP8	Coordinator	
WP9	Providing the requested information in due time in order not to delay the starting of the project	efficacy: WP9	deliverable delayed	2	3	6	WP9 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP9 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board. WP9 creates the robust higher management monitoring that will be established including the oversight of the Executive Board.	deliverable or report due within three months	WP9	WP lead	Lack of Political clarity